

TAUTOLOG

SMARANDACHE LINGUISTIC TAUTOLOGIES

Abstract.

Classes of linguistic tautologies are introduced with examples and explanations.

The general cases exposed below are modeled on the English language structure in a rigid way. In order to find nice particular examples of such tautologies one grammatically adjusts the sentences.

A tautology is a redundancy, a pleonasm, a needless repetition of an idea, according to the "Webster's New World Dictionary", Third College Edition, 1988.

However, the following classes of tautologies - using repetition - go to a deeper meaning, and even changes the sense. A double assertion reverses to a negation. One also may play with the synonyms.

Let <N>, <V>, <A> be some noun, verb, and attribute respectively.

Also let <N'>, <N''>, etc. represent synonyms of <N> (or just <N>), and so <V'>, <V''>, etc.

or <A'>, <A''>, etc.

Let <NV> represent a noun-ed verb, and <NV'> a synonym, etc.

Then, one defines the following classes of linguistic tautologies and semi-tautologies:

1. Mirror semi-paradox:

<N> of the <N'>.

<N> of the <N'> of the <N''>...

Examples:

Best of the best.

Worst of the worst of the worst.

Mother of the mother of the mother... [the maternal grandmother]

Followers of the followers.

The rows of the rows [lots of rows.].

2. This is not an <N>, this is an <N'>.

Examples:

This is not a teacher, this is a professor.

This is not a car, this is a Volkswagen.

This is not a truck, this is a Chevy.

This is not noise, this is music.

This is not music, this is noise.

This is not a cedar tree, this is a <gad> [gad = Navajo name for cedar tree].

This is not me, this is I.

This is not a sword, this is a saber.

This is not a problem, this is an exercise [= easier].

Practice makes you practice.

This is not a girl, this is Katie.

This is not a horse, this is a pony.

3. <N> is not enough <N'>.

<A> is not enough <A'>.

Examples:

Sufficient is not enough sufficient [which means: to do more than

TAUTOLOG

"sufficient"].

Punishment is not enough punishment.

Health is not enough wealth.

Clean is not enough clean.

Studying is not enough studying [which means to do more than just getting by, i.e. to do research].

Extravagant is not enough extravagant.

Time is not enough time.

The more you have, the more you want.

Attention is not enough attention [some people need action too].

4. More <A> than <A'>.

Examples:

Better than better [=perfection].

Worst than worst [=evil].

Sweeter than sweeter [=honey].

More life than life [=spirituality].

More depressed than depressed.

Foster than foster.

More beautiful than pretty.

More ugly than ugly [really ugly].

Smarter than smart [like a genius].

5. How <A> is an <A'> <N>?

Examples:

How democratic is a so called democratic society?

How republican is a so called republic society?

How civilized is a so called civilized person?

How free is a free country?

How commanding is a so called commanding officer?

How Pop Culture is a so called Pop Culture?

How strong is a strong man?

How lone is a lone ranger? [not very, he has tanto].

6. No <A> is really <A'>.

Examples:

No friend is really a friend [s/he betrays you when you don't even expect!].

No luck is really a luck.

No original is really original.

No husband is really a husband [you learn to depend on yourself!].

No tomboy is really a tomboy [girl considered boyish].

No work is really less work.

No true Marxist is really a true Marxist [they contradict their own beliefs].

No magic is really magic [all is only a trick].

7. I would rather prefer <A>, than <A'>.

Examples:

I would rather prefer pretty, than prettier.

I want that, not that.

I would rather prefer this, than this.

I would rather be old, than old.

I would rather prefer great than big.

I would rather be crazy than crazy [crazy like foolish, than crazy like insane].

TAUTOLOG

8. More <A> than <A' >.

Examples:

Prettier than pretty.
More real than real.
More advantage than advantage.
More help than help.
More smiles than smiles [she didn't psychically smile, but there were smiles written all over her face].
More cries than cries.
More meters than kilometers.
Make everyday a rainbow day.
He earns more than himself.
More suspicious than suspected.

9. <V> those who <V' > you.

Examples:

Ignore those who ignore you.
Criticize those who criticize you.
Defend those who defend you.

10. <V>, because <V' >.

Examples:

I want because I want.
I think because I think.
I hear because I listen.
I see because I look.
I need because I need.
I know because I know.
I live because I live.
I believe what is unbelievable [faith].
I am happy because I am happy [there is no reason for my happiness].

11. <V> the <NV' >.

Examples:

I hate the haters (therefore I hate myself!).
I envy the enviers (therefore I envy myself).
I am strange to strangers.
I cheat the cheaters (therefore I cheat myself).
I lie to liars (therefore I lie to myself).
I kick the kickers (therefore I kick myself).
I love the lovers.

The list of such invented linguistic tautologies can be indefinitely extended. It is specific to each language, and it is based on language expressions and types of sentence and phrase constructions and structures.

One can also play with synonymic adverbs, prepositions, etc. to construct other categories of linguistic tautologies.

References:

[1] Ashbacher, Charles, "'The Most Paradoxist Mathematician of the World', by Charles T. Le", review in <Journal of Recreational Mathematics>, USA, Vol. 28(2), 130, 1996-7.

[2] Begay, Anthony, "The Smarandache Semantic Paradox", <Humanistic Mathematics Network Journal>, Harvey Mudd College, Claremont, CA, USA, Issue #17, 48, May 1998.

[3] Le, Charles T., "The Smarandache Class of Paradoxes",

TAUTOLOG

<Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Braşov>, Vol. 1 (36), New Series, Series B, 7-8, 1994.

[4] Le, Charles T., "The Smarandache Class of Paradoxes", <Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences>, Delhi, India, Vol. 14 E (No. 2), 109-110, 1995.

[5] Le, Charles T., "The Most Paradoxist Mathematician of the World: Florentin Smarandache", <Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences>, Delhi, India, Vol. 15E (Mathematics & Statistics), No. 1, 81-100, January-June 1996.

[6] Le, Charles T., "The Smarandache Class of Paradoxes", <Journal of Indian Academy of Mathematics>, Indore, Vol. 18, No. 1, 53-55, 1996.

[7] Le, Charles T., "The Smarandache Class of Paradoxes / (mathematical poem)", <Henry C. Bunner / An Anthology in Memoriam>, Bristol Banner Books, Bristol, IN, USA, 94, 1996.

[8] Mitroiescu, I., "The Smarandache Class of Paradoxes Applied in Computer Sciences", <Abstracts of Papers Presented to the American Mathematical Society>, New Jersey, USA, Vol. 16, No. 3, 651, Issue 101, 1995.

[9] Mudge, Michael R., "A Paradoxist Mathematician: His Function, Paradoxist Geometry, and Class of Paradoxes", <Smarandache Notions Journal>, Vail, AZ, USA, Vol. 7, No. 1-2-3, 127-129, 1996.

[10] Popescu, Marian, "A Model of the Smarandache Paradoxist Geometry", <Abstracts of Papers Presented to the American Mathematical Society>, New Providence, RI, USA, Vol. 17, No. 1, Issue 103, 96T-99-15, 265, 1996.

[11] Popescu, Titu, "Estetica Paradoxismului", Editura Tempus, Bucharest, 26, 27-28, 1995.

[12] Rotaru, Ion, "Din nou despre Florentin Smarandache", <Vatra>, Tg. Mures, Romania, Nr. 2 (299), 93-94, 1996.

[13] Seagull, Larry, "Clasa de Paradoxuri Semantice Smarandache" (in translation), <Abracadabra>, Salinas, CA, USA, Anul 2, Nr. 20, 2, iunie 1994.

[14] Smarandache, Florentin, "Mathematical Fancies & Paradoxes", <The Eugene Strens Memorial on Intuitive and Recreational Mathematics and its History>, University of Calgary, Alberta, Canada, 27 July - 2 August, 1986.

[15] Vasiliu, Florin, "Paradoxism's main roots", Translated from Romanian by Stefan Benea, Xi quan Publishing House, Phoenix, USA, 64 p., 1994; reviewed in <Zentralblatt für Mathematik>, Berlin, No. 5, 830 - 17, 03001, 1996.

[16] Tilton, Homer B., "Smarandache's Paradoxes", <Math Power>, Tucson, AZ, USA, Vol. 2, No. 9, 1-2, September 1996.

[17] Weisstein, Eric W., "CRC Concise Encyclopedia of Mathematics", <Smarandache Paradox>, CRC Press, USA, 1998.

[18] Zitarelli, David E., "Le, Charles T. / The Most Paradoxist Mathematician of the World", <Historia Mathematica>, PA, USA, Vol. 22, No. 4, # 22.4.110, 460, November 1995.

[20] Zitarelli, David E., "Mudge, Michael R. / A Paradoxist Mathematician: His Function, Paradoxist Geometry, and Class of Paradoxes", <Historia Mathematica>, PA, USA, Vol. 24, No. 1, # 24.1.119, 114, February 1997.